

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

International Journal of Solids and Structures

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/ijsostr

An invariant-based elasto-visco-plastic model for unidirectional polymer composites at finite strains

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Unidirectional composites
Finite strains
Visco-plasticity
Visco-elasticity
Constitutive modelling
Invariant theory

ABSTRACT

An invariant-based constitutive model for unidirectional composites, including viscous effects in the elastic and plastic regimes at finite strains, is proposed. The model is based on the multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient, using an isoclinic configuration to avoid the non-uniqueness of intermediate configurations. The visco-elastic behaviour is represented by the generalised Maxwell model, combined with a transversely isotropic yield function and a non-associative plastic potential. Visco-plastic effects are introduced through the Perzyna overstress function. The theoretical basis of the material model and the computational treatment within the finite element solution procedure are presented in detail. Two algorithms are proposed for an implicit integration of the evolution equations: (i) a semi-implicit stress update, and (ii) a fixed-point iterative fully implicit stress update. A comparison of their performance reveals that the former becomes faster, even though the latter guarantees the quadratic convergence rate in the Newton–Raphson scheme. The predicted stress–strain response for different fibre orientation angles is in close agreement with experimental data obtained under quasi-static and dynamic loading. The model can also capture the important re-orientation of the fibres due to external loading.

1. Introduction

The aeronautical, automotive and railway industries are increasingly adopting polymer-based fibre reinforced composite materials to comply with more restrictive regulatory requirements related to fuel consumption and carbon dioxide emissions (Koffler and Rohde-Brandenburg, 2009). The high specific strength and stiffness of polymer composites, along with the possibility to tailor optimised laminates, enable the design and production of components satisfying high-performance requirements with minimum weight.

Fibre-reinforced composites display a stiff and almost linear response in the fibre direction, while highly non-linear behaviour is observed in matrix dominated loadings like longitudinal shear and transverse compression. Additionally, the polymeric matrices exhibit strain-rate dependent behaviour that is also observed in fibre-reinforced composites. Yoon and Sun (1991) performed tests to determine the strain rate effects in AS4/PEEK. Vogler and Kyriakides (1999) experimentally investigated the non-linear behaviour of unidirectional AS4/PEEK and observed that the visco-plastic parameter is very close to the value obtained for neat PEEK, even at room temperature. In the experimental work of Boria et al. (2016), where a thermoplastic composite was tested, the dependence of the elastic modulus, strength and

ductility on the strain rate is clearly observed. Visco-elastic and visco-plastic effects are also observed in carbon–epoxy composites (Koerber et al., 2010, 2018; Fourest and Berthe, 2021).

The use of fibre-reinforced composites in engineering applications requires the development of appropriate constitutive models to predict their mechanical behaviour for arbitrary loading conditions effectively. For meso-scale models where each ply is modelled as a homogeneous material, anisotropy must be considered for both elastic and inelastic regimes, according to the fibre orientation. Sun and Chen (1989) proposed an anisotropic plasticity model characterised by a single parameter to predict the non-linear behaviour of unidirectional composites. This model employs a coordinate transformation law to account for different fibre orientations. Gates and Sun (1991) combined these plasticity constitutive equations with the concept of overstress to obtain a visco-plastic model. However, these models are only valid under the plane stress assumption. Vaziri et al. (1991) presented a constitutive model to predict the non-linear response of laminated composites, considering ultimate failure, but the authors did not include strain rate effects. Vogler et al. (2013) proposed a fully three-dimensional elasto-plastic model for unidirectional composites based on the invariant theory. The results showed good accuracy in the modelling of

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsostr.2021.111292>

Received 15 June 2021; Received in revised form 27 September 2021; Accepted 4 October 2021

Available online 16 October 2021

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thermoset-based composites subjected to arbitrary loading directions. Viscous effects have been included in this model by Koerber et al. (2018) to capture the strain rate dependence. Visco-plastic effects were introduced through the Perzyna overstress function (Perzyna, 1963). At the same time, a scaling law was proposed to capture the influence of the strain rate on the elastic response. Gerbaud et al. (2019) further improved this model by including a visco-elastic law based on a generalised Maxwell model. Only two parameters are required to calibrate the visco-elastic response of transversely isotropic composites. Numerical results demonstrated the accuracy of this model to capture the behaviour of composites loaded in arbitrary directions at different strain rates. More recently, a spectral visco-elastic model was employed by Fourest and Berthe (2021) to simulate strain rate effects on the failure of unidirectional composites.

Invariant theories enable the representation of anisotropy through isotropic tensorial functions. Therefore, this kind of approach is appropriate to model the behaviour of materials displaying preferential orientations, which is the case of unidirectional composites (Boehler, 1987; Spencer, 1992). Anisotropy is introduced in the resulting constitutive equations, for both elastic and inelastic regimes, through the concept of structural tensor, which is obtained from unit vectors defining the material preferential directions. In the case of unidirectional composites, it is merely constructed from the unit vector defining the fibre direction. The work of Vogler et al. (2013), Koerber et al. (2018) and Gerbaud et al. (2019) demonstrate the successful application of this approach to model the complex behaviour of thermoset-based composites. These constitutive models rely on the additive decomposition of the strain tensor, which is compatible with the small strain assumption. Finite strain formulations based on the multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient are well-established to describe materials undergoing more significant deformations. The underlying description of the deformation kinematics can account for the influence of the fibres re-orientation in the constitutive model. Sansour et al. (2007) developed a formulation for anisotropic elasto-plasticity based on the multiplicative decomposition, which is invariant with respect to the intermediate configuration. Eidel (2004) employed the concept of isoclinic configuration in the multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient to overcome the non-uniqueness of the intermediate configuration. This model was combined with an invariant theory to develop a finite strain constitutive model with orthotropic elastic free energy function, orthotropic yield criterion and associative flow rule. Dean et al. (2016b) applied this framework to develop and implement an elasto-plastic model for short fibre reinforced composites. Thermal effects have also been included by the same authors (Dean et al., 2016a, 2017), which may be of great interest to model the processing of thermoplastic composites, through thermoforming for instance. However, neither visco-elastic nor visco-plastic effects are considered in these models.

In the present contribution, an invariant-based visco-elastic-visco-plastic constitutive model for unidirectional composites is developed at finite strains. The model relies on the multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient, considering the so-called isoclinic configuration. A transversely isotropic elastic relation is combined with an invariant-based transversely isotropic yield function. The non-associative visco-plastic potential and the Perzyna overstress function define the visco-plastic effects. Visco-elasticity is introduced by a suitable extension of the approach employed by Gerbaud et al. (2019) for the present finite strain framework. The complete model is presented in Section 2. In Section 3, the numerical implementation of the constitutive model is described in detail. Two stress update algorithms are proposed to guarantee an implicit integration of the evolution equations, and are assessed in terms of computational performance. Numerical results obtained through finite element simulations are presented in Section 4. The results of off-axis tension and compression simulations are compared with experimental data and with numerical results obtained with an approach based on the additive decomposition of the strain tensor. The ability of the present model to capture changes in fibre orientations is also illustrated in Section 4. The main conclusions are summarised in Section 5.

Fig. 1. Representation of the reference (Ω_0), isoclinic ($\hat{\Omega}$), intermediate ($\tilde{\Omega}$) and final (Ω) configurations, and the quantities employed to map between these configurations.

2. Constitutive modelling

2.1. Kinematics

As the starting point, it is fundamental to clearly establish the kinematic relations defining the finite strain deformation of a composite. The deformation gradient F is employed in the mapping between the reference (undeformed) and the final (deformed) configuration. The contributions of elastic and plastic deformation mechanisms are introduced through the so-called *multiplicative decomposition* of the deformation gradient, defined by

$$F = F^p F^e, \quad (1)$$

where F^p denotes the visco-plastic deformation gradient, mapping between the reference and intermediate configurations, and F^e represents the visco-elastic deformation gradient that maps from the intermediate to the final configuration. Due to the non-uniqueness of the intermediate configuration, the approach where the isoclinic configuration is conveniently introduced is employed here. This concept has been used by Eidel (2004) in the context of crystal plasticity and has been recently employed in a model for short fibre composites by Dean et al. (2016b). The isoclinic configuration is defined as the intermediate configuration where the director vectors defining the material anisotropy coincide with their counterparts in the reference configuration and remain fixed during the deformation. It differs from the general intermediate configuration only by a rigid body rotation. The mapping between the reference and the isoclinic configuration is performed by the second-order tensor \tilde{F}^p . The isoclinic configuration is mapped to the general intermediate configuration by the rotation Φ . These configurations are represented in Fig. 1, where a denotes the director vector that defines the fibre direction for unidirectional composites. It must be remarked that intermediate configurations are an abstract concept representing the state in which the material is locally unstressed. They do not comply with the compatibility conditions and there is no admissible intermediate configuration where the entire body deformation can be represented. This is the reason why only an infinitesimal volume has been represented in both isoclinic and intermediate configuration, in Fig. 1.

Due to the interesting and convenient properties of the isoclinic configuration, the constitutive relations can be expressed in this particular configuration. The definitions of the relevant strain and stress measures, along with fundamental kinematics relations, are presented in the remaining of this section:

General notation:

$$(\hat{\bullet}) - \text{quantity } \bullet \text{ in the intermediate configuration} \quad (2)$$

($\bar{\bullet}$) – quantity \bullet in the isoclinic configuration (3)

Fundamental kinematics:

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{F}^e \mathbf{F}^p = \mathbf{F}^e \Phi \tilde{\mathbf{F}}^p \quad (\text{deformation gradient}) \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{J} = \det \mathbf{F} \quad (\text{determinant of the deformation gradient}) \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{R} \quad (\text{polar decomposition}) \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) \quad (\text{velocity}) \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{L} = \dot{\mathbf{F}}\mathbf{F}^{-1} = \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{W} \quad (\text{velocity gradient}) \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{D} = \text{sym } \mathbf{L} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{L} + \mathbf{L}^T) \quad (\text{rate of deformation}) \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{W} = \text{skew } \mathbf{L} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{L} - \mathbf{L}^T) \quad (\text{spin}) \quad (10)$$

Strain measures:

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F} \quad (\text{right Cauchy–Green tensor}) \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}^T \quad (\text{left Cauchy–Green tensor}) \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{C} - \mathbf{I}) \quad (\text{Green–Lagrange tensor}) \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{C}^p = \mathbf{F}^{pT} \mathbf{F}^p \quad (\text{plastic left Cauchy–Green tensor}) \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{E}^p = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{C}^p - \mathbf{I}) \quad (\text{plastic Green–Lagrange tensor}) \quad (15)$$

Isoclinic configuration:

$$\mathbf{F}^p = \Phi \tilde{\mathbf{F}}^p \Leftrightarrow \tilde{\mathbf{F}}^p = \Phi^T \mathbf{F}^p \quad (\text{isoclinic plastic deformation gradient}) \quad (16)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e = \Phi^T \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e \Phi \quad (\text{isoclinic elastic Green–Lagrange tensor}) \quad (17)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{L}}^p = \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{F}}^p} [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}^p]^{-1} = \Phi^T (\hat{\mathbf{L}}^p - \Phi \Phi^T) \Phi \quad (\text{isoclinic plastic velocity gradient}) \quad (18)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}^e = [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}^p]^{-T} \mathbf{C} [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}^p]^{-1} \quad (\text{isoclinic elastic left Cauchy–Green tensor}) \quad (19)$$

Stress measures:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{J}^{-1} \mathbf{F} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{F}^T \quad (\text{Cauchy stress tensor}) \quad (20)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}} = \mathbf{C}^e : \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e = \Phi \hat{\mathbf{S}} \Phi^T \quad (\text{isoclinic second Piola–Kirchhoff stress tensor}) \quad (21)$$

$$\mathbf{S} = (\tilde{\mathbf{F}}^p)^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{S}} (\tilde{\mathbf{F}}^p)^{-T} \quad (\text{second Piola–Kirchhoff stress tensor}) \quad (22)$$

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}} = \tilde{\mathbf{C}}^e \tilde{\mathbf{S}} \quad (\text{isoclinic Mandel stress tensor}) \quad (23)$$

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s = \text{sym } \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}} = \frac{1}{2} (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}} + \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}^T) \quad (\text{symmetric isoclinic Mandel stress tensor}) \quad (24)$$

2.2. Elastic-free energy function

Based on the invariant theory, the elastic-free energy function can be defined as a function of the isoclinic elastic Green–Lagrange strain tensor and the structural tensor (Dean et al., 2016b; Eidel, 2004). For a transversely isotropic material, it can be defined as

$$\Psi^e(\tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e, \tilde{\mathbf{A}}) = \frac{\lambda}{2} J_1^2 + \mu_T J_2 + \alpha J_3 J_1 + 2(\mu_L - \mu_T) J_4 + \frac{\beta}{2} J_3^2, \quad (25)$$

where the invariants J_1 to J_4 are expressed in terms of $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ as

$$J_1 = \text{tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e), \quad (26)$$

$$J_2 = \text{tr}([\tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e]^2), \quad (27)$$

$$J_3 = \text{tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e), \quad (28)$$

$$J_4 = \text{tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}} [\tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e]^2), \quad (29)$$

and the elastic constants are obtained from their engineering counterparts as:

$$\lambda = \frac{E_{22}(v_{23} + v_{31}v_{13})}{D} \quad (30)$$

$$\alpha = E_{22} \frac{v_{31}(1 + v_{32} - v_{13}) - v_{32}}{D} \quad (31)$$

$$\beta = E_{11} \frac{1 - v_{32}v_{23}}{D} - E_{22} \frac{1 - v_{21}[v_{12} + 2(1 + v_{23})]}{D} - 4G_{12} \quad (32)$$

$$\mu_L = G_{12} \quad (33)$$

$$\mu_T = G_{23} \quad (34)$$

$$D = 1 - v_{32}^2 - 2v_{13}v_{31} - 2v_{32}v_{13}v_{31}. \quad (35)$$

The reference director vector \mathbf{a}_0 is a unit vector defined *a priori* according to the fibre direction. The structural tensor, in the isoclinic configuration, is determined from the isoclinic director vector $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}$ as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \tilde{\mathbf{a}} \otimes \tilde{\mathbf{a}}. \quad (36)$$

The vector $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}$ can be mapped from their reference counterpart through

$$\tilde{\mathbf{a}} = \tilde{\mathbf{F}}^p \mathbf{a}_0. \quad (37)$$

Even though this transformation guarantees that \mathbf{a}_0 and $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}$ remain aligned, the latter is not necessarily a unit vector. Therefore, it is assumed that $\tilde{\mathbf{a}} = \mathbf{a}_0$ in order to keep the elastic relation physically consistent (Eidel, 2004).

The elastic stress–strain relation is defined in terms of the isoclinic second Piola–Kirchhoff stress tensor, which is expressed by:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}}(\tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e, \tilde{\mathbf{A}}) = \frac{\partial \Psi^e(\tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e, \tilde{\mathbf{A}})}{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e} = \lambda \text{tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e) \mathbf{I} + 2\mu_T \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e + \alpha [\text{tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e) + \text{tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e) \tilde{\mathbf{A}}] \mathbf{I} + 2(\mu_L - \mu_T)(\tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e \tilde{\mathbf{A}} + \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e) + \beta \text{tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e) \tilde{\mathbf{A}}. \quad (38)$$

The elastic modulus can be obtained through

$$\mathbf{C}^e = \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e} = \frac{\partial^2 \Psi^e}{\partial [\tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e]^2}. \quad (39)$$

2.3. The invariant-based transversely isotropic yield function

An invariant-based transversely isotropic yield function suitable for unidirectional composites is introduced here. The approach employed by Vogler et al. (2013) is extended to the finite strain setting, leading to the yield function defined by

$$f(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s, \tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \bar{\epsilon}^p) = \alpha_1 I_1 + \alpha_2 I_2 + \alpha_3 I_3 + \alpha_{32} I_3^2 - 1 \leq 0, \quad (40)$$

where the parameters α_i are obtained from calibration through the hardening curves, defining the evolution of the yield surface with accumulated plastic deformation $\bar{\epsilon}^p$. The invariants I_1 to I_3 are expressed as:

$$I_1 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\text{tr} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s^{\text{pind}} \right)^2 - \text{tr} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{A}} [\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s^{\text{pind}}]^2 \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\text{tr} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s^{\text{pind}} \right)^2 - \tilde{\mathbf{a}} [\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s^{\text{pind}}]^2 \tilde{\mathbf{a}}, \quad (41)$$

$$I_2 = \text{tr} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{A}} [\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s^{\text{pind}}]^2 \right) = \tilde{\mathbf{a}} [\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s^{\text{pind}}]^2 \tilde{\mathbf{a}}, \quad (42)$$

$$I_3 = \text{tr} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s - \text{tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s) = \text{tr} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s - \tilde{\mathbf{a}} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s \tilde{\mathbf{a}}, \quad (43)$$

where $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s^{\text{pind}}$ denotes the plasticity component of the stress tensor. The decomposition of the symmetric isoclinic Mandel stress tensor into the plasticity and the reaction stress components is defined by:

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s^{\text{react}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\text{tr}(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s) - \tilde{\mathbf{a}} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s \tilde{\mathbf{a}} \right) \mathbf{I} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\text{tr}(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s) - 3\tilde{\mathbf{a}} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s \tilde{\mathbf{a}} \right) \tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \quad (44)$$

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s^{\text{pind}} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_s^{\text{react}}. \quad (45)$$

The definition of these invariants in terms of the symmetric part of the isoclinic Mandel stress tensor, which is generally unsymmetric, allows

to implicitly account for the isoclinic rotation Φ in the constitutive model, as explained in Section 2.4. Consequently, only the symmetric part of the isoclinic Mandel stress tensor is assumed to contribute to the yielding process in order to maintain the consistency between the invariants employed in the yield function and the plastic potential.

2.3.1. Determination of the hardening parameters

The parameters α_i are determined from hardening curves obtained for different stress states. Following Vogler et al. (2013), for a given level of accumulated plastic strain $\bar{\epsilon}^p$, the values of the yield stress for transverse shear (tr), in-plane shear (ip), uniaxial tension and compression (ut and uc), and biaxial tension and compression (bt and bc) are obtained. The hardening parameters are related to these values using the following equations:

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{1}{\sigma_{Y, \text{tr}}^2} \quad (46)$$

$$\alpha_2 = \frac{1}{\sigma_{Y, \text{ip}}^2} \quad (47)$$

$$\alpha_{32}^c = \frac{1 - \frac{\sigma_{Y, \text{uc}}}{2\sigma_{Y, \text{bc}}} - \frac{1}{4}\alpha_1\sigma_{Y, \text{uc}}^2}{\sigma_{Y, \text{uc}}^2 - 2\sigma_{Y, \text{bc}}\sigma_{Y, \text{uc}}} \quad (48)$$

$$\alpha_3^c = \frac{-1 + 4\alpha_{32}^c\sigma_{Y, \text{bc}}^2}{2\sigma_{Y, \text{bc}}} \quad (49)$$

$$\alpha_{32}^t = \frac{1 - \frac{\sigma_{Y, \text{ut}}}{2\sigma_{Y, \text{bt}}} - \frac{1}{4}\alpha_1\sigma_{Y, \text{ut}}^2}{\sigma_{Y, \text{ut}}^2 - 2\sigma_{Y, \text{bt}}\sigma_{Y, \text{ut}}} \quad (50)$$

$$\alpha_3^t = \frac{1 - 4\alpha_{32}^t\sigma_{Y, \text{bt}}^2}{2\sigma_{Y, \text{bt}}} \quad (51)$$

Note that there is a distinction between tension and compression states in the definition of α_3 and α_{32} :

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_3 &= \alpha_3^t, & \alpha_{32} &= \alpha_{32}^t & \text{if } I_3 > 0, \\ \alpha_3 &= \alpha_3^c, & \alpha_{32} &= \alpha_{32}^c & \text{if } I_3 \leq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

The evolution of the internal variable is defined through the isoclinic rate of plastic deformation as

$$\dot{\bar{\epsilon}}^p = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \bar{\mathbf{D}}^p : \bar{\mathbf{D}}^p}. \quad (53)$$

Note that the factor $\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}}$ employed here does not correspond to the conventional von Mises equivalent strain, typically used in metal plasticity and short-fibre composites (Dean et al., 2016b), where the factor is $\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}$. As pointed out by Vogler (2012), the factor $\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}}$ corresponds to the definition of the uniaxial plastic strain under uniaxial stress states perpendicular to the fibres, for incompressible plastic deformation in uni-directional composites. In the general case of compressible plastic deformation, considered here through a non-associative visco-plastic potential (Section 2.4), additional correction factors are required to adapt the accumulated plastic strain definition to the hardening curve corresponding to a given stress state. Additional details regarding the determination of these parameters are found in the contributions of Vogler (2012), Vogler et al. (2013).

2.4. Visco-plastic potential and flow rule

The non-associative visco-plastic potential is defined through the invariant form:

$$g(\bar{\Sigma}_s, \bar{\mathbf{A}}) = \beta_1 I_1 + \beta_2 I_2 + \beta_{32} I_3^2 - 1 = \frac{1}{2} \bar{\Sigma}_s : \mathbb{M} : \bar{\Sigma}_s, \quad (54)$$

The use of a non-associative flow rule allows to properly account for the plastic volumetric deformations observed in polymeric materials and polymer-based composites (Vogler et al., 2013; Melro et al., 2013). As pointed out by Eidel (2004), by assuming that only the symmetric part

of the isoclinic Mandel stress tensor contributes to the plastic potential, the skew part of the plastic velocity gradient $\bar{\mathbf{L}}^p$ vanishes, i.e., $\bar{\mathbf{W}}^p = \mathbf{0}$. This is quite convenient since it allows to account for the rotation Φ implicitly in the constitutive model.

Therefore, the evolution of the plastic deformation is defined by the following flow rule (Dean et al., 2016b):

$$\bar{\mathbf{D}}^p = \dot{\gamma} \mathbf{N}_g, \quad (55)$$

where the flow tensor is obtained as

$$\mathbf{N}_g = \frac{\partial g(\bar{\Sigma}_s, \bar{\mathbf{A}})}{\partial \bar{\Sigma}_s} = \mathbb{M} : \bar{\Sigma}_s, \quad (56)$$

The parameters are computed from *plastic potential stresses*, $\hat{\sigma}$, which are calibrated to guarantee a given value of the plastic Poisson's ratio (Vogler et al., 2013):

$$\beta_1 = \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}_{tr}^2} \quad (57)$$

$$\beta_2 = \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}_{ip}^2} \quad (58)$$

$$\beta_{32} = \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}_u} - \frac{\beta_1}{4}. \quad (59)$$

The fourth-order tensor \mathbb{M} is defined by:

$$\mathbb{M} = \beta_1 \mathbb{P}^{\text{pind}} + (\beta_2 - \beta_1) \mathbb{P}_{\bar{\mathbf{A}}}^{\text{pind}} + 2\beta_{32} (\mathbf{I} - \bar{\mathbf{A}}) \otimes (\mathbf{I} - \bar{\mathbf{A}}), \quad (60)$$

with the projection tensors

$$\mathbb{P}^{\text{pind}} = \mathbb{I} + \frac{1}{2} (\bar{\mathbf{A}} \otimes \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{I} \otimes \bar{\mathbf{A}} - \mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{I} - 3\bar{\mathbf{A}} \otimes \bar{\mathbf{A}}), \quad (61)$$

$$\left(\mathbb{P}_{\bar{\mathbf{A}}}^{\text{pind}} \right)_{ijkl} = \bar{\mathbf{A}}_{im} \mathbb{P}_{mjkl}^{\text{pind}} + \bar{\mathbf{A}}_{mj} \mathbb{P}_{imkl}^{\text{pind}}, \quad (62)$$

and $\mathbb{I}_{ijkl} = \delta_{ik}\delta_{jl}$ denoting the fourth-order identity tensor.

2.4.1. Evolution of the plastic multiplier

In strain-rate insensitive models, the evolution of the plastic multiplier is determined by the so-called loading/unloading and consistency conditions that guarantee a stress state compatible with the yielding surface (Vogler et al., 2013; Dean et al., 2016b). Here, visco-plastic effects are introduced through the definition of plastic multiplier evolution according to the Perzyna model (Koerber et al., 2018):

$$\dot{\gamma} = \frac{\langle f^m(\bar{\Sigma}_s, \bar{\mathbf{A}}, \bar{\epsilon}^p) \rangle}{\eta} \quad (63)$$

with η denoting the viscosity parameter and m a non-dimensional parameter, and the Macaulay brackets guaranteeing that $\dot{\gamma} \geq 0$. This evolution induces an overstress that is related to the strain rate. The stress state is not required to lie in the yield surface anymore when plastic deformation occurs.

2.5. Visco-elastic formulation

In addition to visco-plastic effects, also the elastic response of polymeric materials is sensitive to the strain rate. The approach introduced by Gerbaud et al. (2019) to include visco-elastic effects within an invariant-based model is extended here to a finite strain framework. The visco-elastic response is characterised by the rheological model represented in Fig. 2, where a Maxwell element is included in parallel with a Hooke element.

Applying the finite strain theory for visco-elasticity presented by Kaliske (2000) to the isoclinic configuration, the resulting stress can be expressed through

$$\bar{\mathbf{S}}(\bar{\mathbf{E}}^e, \bar{\mathbf{A}}) = \bar{\mathbf{S}}_0 + \bar{\mathbf{S}}_1, \quad (64)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{S}}_0$ is determined from the elastic relation in Eq. (38) and the visco-elastic component is defined by

$$\bar{\mathbf{S}}_1 = \int_0^t \Gamma_1 : \frac{\partial \bar{\mathbf{S}}_0}{\partial t^*} \cdot e^{-\frac{t-t^*}{\tau_1}} dt^*. \quad (65)$$

Fig. 2. Rheological model for visco-elasticity.

The fourth-order tensor Γ_1 is the so-called relaxation tensor and τ_1 is a scalar parameter. Both are considered material constants. Assuming linear evolution of the stress \tilde{S}_0 during each time step, Kaliske (2000) introduced an efficient formula to perform the integration of Eq. (65) in a discrete temporal framework, defined by

$$\tilde{S}_1^{n+1} = e^{-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_1}} \tilde{S}_1^n + \frac{1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_1}}}{\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_1}} \Gamma_1 : (\tilde{S}_0^{n+1} - \tilde{S}_0^n). \quad (66)$$

Concerning the relaxation tensor, Gerbaud et al. (2019) proposed a unique scalar relaxation parameter, γ_1 , by assuming that the relaxation behaviour is similar for the components of the plasticity induced component of the stresses. In fact, Kaliske and Rothert (1997) reported that the visco-elastic behaviour is mainly linked to the isochoric part of the deformation. Therefore, in a framework based on the additive decomposition of the strain tensor, it results in:

$$\Gamma_1 = \gamma_1 \mathbb{I}^{\text{pind}} \Rightarrow \Gamma_1 : \Delta \sigma_0 = \gamma_1 \Delta \sigma_0^{\text{pind}}. \quad (67)$$

The introduction of this assumption in the current finite strain model yields

$$\tilde{S}_1^{n+1} = e^{-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_1}} \tilde{S}_1^n + \frac{1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_1}}}{\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_1}} \gamma_1 (\tilde{S}_{0,n+1}^{\text{pind}} - \tilde{S}_{0,n}^{\text{pind}}). \quad (68)$$

This requires the determination of the plasticity-induced component of the isoclinic second Piola–Kirchhoff stress tensor. However, as introduced in Section 2.3, the plasticity-induced component of the stresses is determined from the isoclinic Mandel stress tensor. Therefore, for the sake of consistency, the value of $\tilde{S}_{0,n+1}$ is transformed to its Mandel stress tensor counterpart $\tilde{\Sigma}_{0,n+1}$ in the first place:

$$\tilde{\Sigma}_{0,n+1} = \tilde{C}_{n+1}^e \cdot \tilde{S}_{0,n+1}. \quad (69)$$

Then, the plasticity induced component is determined according to Eq. (45):

$$\tilde{\Sigma}_{0,n+1}^{\text{pind}} = \tilde{\Sigma}_{0,n+1} - \tilde{\Sigma}_{0,n+1}^{\text{reac}}. \quad (70)$$

Finally, the corresponding isoclinic second Piola–Kirchhoff stress tensor is recovered:

$$\tilde{S}_{0,n+1}^{\text{pind}} = [\tilde{C}_{n+1}^e]^{-1} \cdot \tilde{\Sigma}_{0,n+1}^{\text{pind}}. \quad (71)$$

3. Numerical implementation

The present constitutive model is implemented in a user-material subroutine VUMAT (Abaqus, 2017) for Abaqus/Explicit so that it can be employed in finite element simulations. An incremental boundary-value problem solution is considered, where time is discretised in a finite number of increments characterised by $t_{n+1} = t_n + \Delta t$. The stresses and state variables must be updated at each integration point according to the constitutive equations. The evolution laws are consistently integrated for each time increment to perform the state update.

A visco-elastic trial/visco-plastic corrector approach is adopted here along with an implicit backward-Euler integration scheme to integrate the constitutive model (de Souza Neto et al., 2008). In the visco-elastic trial state, it is assumed that the increment of deformation in the interval $[t_n, t_{n+1}]$ is purely visco-elastic, i.e., $\tilde{F}_{n+1}^p = \tilde{F}_n^p$, to obtain the elastic trial Green–Lagrange tensor $\tilde{E}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}$ and update the trial stress tensor $\tilde{S}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}$. This assumption is tested by evaluating the yield function value with the trial stress state. The visco-elastic trial state is valid if $f(\tilde{\Sigma}_{s,n+1}^{\text{trial}}, \tilde{A}, \tilde{\epsilon}_n^p) < 0$. Otherwise, the plastic deformation gradient must be updated. Given the implicit scheme adopted:

$$\tilde{F}_{n+1}^p = \tilde{F}_n^p + \Delta t \dot{\tilde{F}}_{n+1}^p. \quad (72)$$

Additionally, due to the fact that $\tilde{W}^p = \mathbf{0}$, we can state that $\tilde{L}^p = \tilde{D}^p$. This definition, combined with Eq. (55), allows writing

$$\tilde{D}_{n+1}^p = \dot{\tilde{F}}_{n+1}^p [\tilde{F}_{n+1}^p]^{-1} = \dot{\gamma}_{n+1} \mathbf{N}_{g,n+1} \quad (73)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \dot{\tilde{F}}_{n+1}^p = \dot{\gamma}_{n+1} \mathbf{N}_{g,n+1} \tilde{F}_{n+1}^p. \quad (74)$$

Introducing Eq. (74) into Eq. (72), with $\Delta \gamma_{n+1} = \Delta t \dot{\gamma}_{n+1}$, allows to express the updated plastic deformation gradient as

$$\tilde{F}_{n+1}^p = [\mathbf{I} - \Delta \gamma_{n+1} \mathbf{N}_{g,n+1}]^{-1} \tilde{F}_n^p. \quad (75)$$

In the numerical implementation, it is more convenient to deal with the inverse of the plastic deformation gradient instead, which can be updated through

$$[\tilde{F}_{n+1}^p]^{-1} = [\tilde{F}_n^p]^{-1} \cdot [\mathbf{I} - \Delta \gamma_{n+1} \mathbf{N}_{g,n+1}]. \quad (76)$$

Therefore, the incremental plastic multiplier must be determined. The time-discrete version of Eq. (63) leads to

$$\Delta \gamma_{n+1} = \Delta t \cdot \frac{f^m(\tilde{\Sigma}_{s,n+1}, \tilde{A}, \tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^p)}{\eta}, \quad (77)$$

which can be rewritten as

$$f^m(\Delta \gamma_{n+1}) - \eta \frac{\Delta \gamma_{n+1}}{\Delta t} = 0. \quad (78)$$

The iterative Newton–Raphson scheme is employed to solve this non-linear equation, determine $\Delta \gamma_{n+1}$, and update the stress and state variables. Given the value of the residual in a generic iteration k :

$$r^{(k)} = f^m(\Delta \gamma_{n+1}^{(k)}) - \eta \frac{\Delta \gamma_{n+1}^{(k)}}{\Delta t}, \quad (79)$$

the plastic multiplier is updated for a new iteration $k + 1$ through

$$\Delta \gamma_{n+1}^{(k+1)} = \Delta \gamma_{n+1}^{(k)} - \frac{r^{(k)}}{\frac{\partial f^m}{\partial \Delta \gamma_{n+1}}}. \quad (80)$$

The residual derivative is obtained by

$$\frac{\partial r^{(k)}}{\partial \Delta \gamma_{n+1}} = m f^{m-1}(\Delta \gamma_{n+1}^{(k)}) \frac{\partial f(\Delta \gamma_{n+1})}{\partial \Delta \gamma_{n+1}} \Big|_{\Delta \gamma_{n+1} = \Delta \gamma_{n+1}^{(k)}} - \frac{\eta}{\Delta t}. \quad (81)$$

Due to the significantly complex relation between the yield function value f and $\Delta \gamma_{n+1}$, the derivative $\partial f / \partial \Delta \gamma_{n+1}$ is numerically determined through forward finite differences. Numerical experience has shown that a perturbation value of $\epsilon = 10^{-6}$ is adequate and that the use of the finite difference method to obtain the derivative in Eq. (81) takes around 50% of each iteration computing time. This value agrees with the expectations since this method repeats the stress update procedure with a slightly perturbed value of the plastic multiplier. As illustrated in Section 4.3, quadratic convergence is achieved in the Newton–Raphson iterative scheme employing this strategy.

The visco-elastic trial/visco-plastic corrector algorithm is presented in Box 1, with the iterative solution of Eq. (78) being detailed in Box 2. It must be highlighted that, even though these algorithms are implemented in the framework of explicit finite element simulations, they can be employed in implicit analyses. The only additional derivation is related to the determination of the consistent tangent modulus.

Box 1 State update algorithm based on visco-elastic trial/visco-plastic corrector.

Given the current total deformation gradient, the increment of time and the previous state variables

$$\mathbf{F}_{n+1}, \Delta t, [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_n^p]^{-1}, \tilde{\varepsilon}_n^p, \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{1,n}, \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{0,n}^{\text{pind}}$$

i. Determine the visco-elastic trial state:

$$\mathbf{C}_{n+1} = \mathbf{F}_{n+1}^T \mathbf{F}_{n+1}$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{n+1}^{\text{e trial}} = [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_n^p]^{-T} \mathbf{C}_{n+1} [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_n^p]^{-1}$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{n+1}^{\text{e trial}} = \frac{1}{2} (\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{n+1}^{\text{e trial}} - \mathbf{I})$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{0,n+1}^{\text{e trial}} = \mathbf{C}^e : \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{n+1}^{\text{e trial}}$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{1,n+1}^{\text{e trial}} = \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_1 (\Delta t, \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{1,n}, \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{0,n}^{\text{pind trial}})$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{n+1}^{\text{e trial}} = \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{0,n+1}^{\text{e trial}} + \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{1,n+1}^{\text{e trial}}$$

$$\tilde{\Sigma}_{n+1}^{\text{e trial}} = \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{n+1}^{\text{e trial}} \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{n+1}^{\text{e trial}}$$

$$\tilde{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p trial}} = \tilde{\varepsilon}_n^p$$

ii. Evaluate the yield function

$$f_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} = f(\tilde{\Sigma}_{s,n+1}^{\text{e trial}}, \tilde{\Lambda}, \tilde{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{\text{p trial}})$$

If $f_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} \leq 0$:

$$(\bullet)_{n+1} = (\bullet)_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}$$

go to iv.

iii. Proceed to the visco-plastic corrector. Determine the incremental visco-plastic multiplier $\Delta\gamma_{n+1}$ through the solution of:

$$f^m(\Delta\gamma_{n+1}) - \eta \frac{\Delta\gamma_{n+1}}{\Delta t_{n+1}} = 0.$$

See Box 2.

iv. With the updated plastic deformation gradient, stress measures and internal variables, compute the Cauchy stress tensor

$$\mathbf{S}_{n+1} = [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{n+1}^p]^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{n+1} [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{n+1}^p]^{-T}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1} = \frac{1}{\det \mathbf{F}_{n+1}} \mathbf{F}_{n+1} \mathbf{S}_{n+1} \mathbf{F}_{n+1}^T$$

and save the state variables

$$[\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{n+1}^p]^{-1}, \tilde{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p, \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{0,n+1}^{\text{pind}}, \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{1,n+1}.$$

3.1. Iterative isoclinic Mandel stress update

Within the local Newton–Raphson scheme, the isoclinic Mandel stress tensor must be updated at each iteration according to the procedure described in point iv of Box 2. However, the updated $\tilde{\Sigma}_{n+1}$ depends on the updated flow tensor $\mathbf{N}_{g,n+1}$, which depends on $\tilde{\Sigma}_{n+1}$ itself. Therefore, the definition of a closed-form expression to perform the isoclinic Mandel stress update is a cumbersome task. Two alternative strategies are addressed in this contribution to deal with this difficulty: (i) a semi-implicit approach and (ii) an iterative fixed-point approach to guarantee a fully implicit stress update.

3.1.1. Semi-implicit stress update

In the semi-implicit approach, for a generic iteration k within the local Newton–Raphson, it is assumed that the flow tensor is updated according to the isoclinic Mandel stress tensor from the previous iteration:

$$\mathbf{N}_{g,n+1} = \mathbb{M} : \tilde{\Sigma}_{s,n+1}^{(k-1)} \quad (82)$$

Box 2 Local Newton–Raphson algorithm.

Initialise the iterative cycle:

$$k = 0, \Delta\gamma_{n+1}^{(k)} = 0, f_{n+1}^{(k)} = f_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}, r^{(k)} = (f_{n+1}^{\text{trial}})^m$$

i. Start a new iteration: $k = k + 1$

ii. Compute the residual derivative $\partial r^{(k-1)} / \Delta\gamma_{n+1}$

iii. Update the plastic multiplier

$$\delta\Delta\gamma = -\frac{r^{(k-1)}}{\frac{\partial r^{(k-1)}}{\partial \Delta\gamma_{n+1}}}$$

$$\Delta\gamma_{n+1}^{(k)} = \Delta\gamma_{n+1}^{(k-1)} + \delta\Delta\gamma$$

iv. Compute the plastic flow tensor and update accumulated plastic strain, plastic deformation gradient and stresses

$$\mathbf{N}_{g,n+1} = \mathbb{M} : \tilde{\Sigma}_{s,n+1}$$

$$\tilde{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p = \tilde{\varepsilon}_n^p + \Delta\gamma_{n+1}^{(k)} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}} \|\mathbf{N}_{g,n+1}\|$$

$$[\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{n+1}^p]^{-1} = [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_n^p]^{-1} [\mathbf{I} - \Delta\gamma_{n+1}^{(k)} \mathbf{N}_{g,n+1}]$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{n+1}^{\text{e}} = [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{n+1}^p]^{-T} \mathbf{C}_{n+1} [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{n+1}^p]^{-1}$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{n+1}^{\text{e}} = \frac{1}{2} (\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{n+1}^{\text{e}} - \mathbf{I})$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{0,n+1}^{\text{e}} = \mathbf{C}^e : \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{n+1}^{\text{e}}$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{n+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{0,n+1}^{\text{e}} + \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{1,n+1}$$

$$\tilde{\Sigma}_{n+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{n+1}^{\text{e}} \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{n+1}$$

v. Update the hardening parameters, compute the invariants and evaluate the yield function value

$$\alpha_1 = \alpha_1(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p), \alpha_2 = \alpha_2(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p), \alpha_3 = \alpha_3(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p), \alpha_{32} = \alpha_{32}(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p)$$

$$I_1 = I_1(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \tilde{\Sigma}_{s,n+1}), I_2 = I_2(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \tilde{\Sigma}_{s,n+1}), I_3 = I_3(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \tilde{\Sigma}_{s,n+1})$$

$$f_{n+1}^{(k)} = \alpha_1 I_1 + \alpha_2 I_2 + \alpha_3 I_3 + \alpha_{32} I_3^2$$

vi. Evaluate the new residual and check convergence:

$$r^{(k)} = (f_{n+1}^{(k)})^m - \eta \frac{\Delta\gamma_{n+1}}{\Delta t_{n+1}}$$

If $r^{(k)} \leq \epsilon_{\text{tol}}$:

$$(\bullet)_{n+1} = (\bullet)_{n+1}^{(k)}$$

go to vii

Else, proceed with a new iteration, go to i

vii. Convergence has been achieved. Return the updated stress and state variables.

Due to the quadratic convergence rate observed in Newton–Raphson schemes, the difference between stresses in two consecutive iterations becomes negligible when approaching the solution. Therefore, when the converged solution is achieved, this semi-implicit approach should recover the fully implicit one.

3.1.2. Fixed-point iterative stress update

To guarantee that a fully implicit stress update is performed, a fixed-point iterative approach is employed to undertake the procedure described in point iv of Box 2. The resulting algorithm is summarised in Box 3.

The main drawback related to this approach lies in the additional iterative process included in each iteration of the local Newton–Raphson scheme. Nevertheless, it may be fundamental to achieve quadratic convergence and guarantee that the return-mapping algorithm succeeds. A comparative study of these alternatives is presented in Section 4.3.

Box 3 A fixed-point iterative algorithm for fully-implicit stress update.

Within a generic iteration k in the local Newton–Raphson scheme, initialise a new iteration counter and set the guess value of the isoclinic Mandel stress tensor:

$$l = 0, \quad \tilde{\Sigma}_{n+1}^{guess} = \tilde{\Sigma}_{n+1}^{(k-1)}$$

- i. Start a new iteration: $l = l + 1$
- ii. Update the flow tensor with the guess of the isoclinic Mandel stress tensor:

$$\mathbf{N}_{g,n+1} = \mathbb{M} : \tilde{\Sigma}_{s,n+1}^{guess}$$

- iii. Update the plastic deformation gradient and stress measures

$$[\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{n+1}^p]^{-1} = [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_n^p]^{-1} \left[\mathbf{I} - \Delta\gamma_{n+1}^{(k)} \mathbf{N}_{g,n+1} \right]$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{n+1}^e = [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{n+1}^p]^{-T} \mathbf{C}_{n+1} [\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{n+1}^p]^{-1}$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{n+1}^e = \frac{1}{2} (\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{n+1}^e - \mathbf{I})$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{0,n+1} = \mathbf{C}^e : \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{n+1}^e$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{n+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{0,n+1} + \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{1,n+1}$$

$$\tilde{\Sigma}_{n+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{n+1}^e \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_{n+1}$$

- iv. Evaluate the quality of the guess:

$$\epsilon_{\tilde{\Sigma}} = \frac{\|\tilde{\Sigma}_{n+1} - \tilde{\Sigma}_{n+1}^{guess}\|}{\|\tilde{\Sigma}_{n+1}^{(k-1)}\|}$$

- v. If $\epsilon_{\tilde{\Sigma}} \leq \epsilon_{\tilde{\Sigma},tol}$, update the accumulated plastic strain and return the updated stress value

$$\tilde{\epsilon}_{n+1}^p = \tilde{\epsilon}_n^p + \Delta\gamma_{n+1}^{(k)} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{N}_{g,n+1}\|}.$$

Else, update the guess

$$\tilde{\Sigma}_{n+1}^{guess} = \tilde{\Sigma}_{n+1}.$$

and proceed with a new iteration, go to **i**

Table 1

Viscous parameters employed in the simulations with IM7-8552.

τ_1	10^{-2} s
γ_1	0.32
m	1
η	3.5×10^{-4} Ns/mm ²

Table 2

Elastic properties employed to model IM7-8552 (Koerber et al., 2018).

E_{11}	171.42 GPa
E_{22}	8.93 GPa
G_{12}	5.10 GPa
ν_{12}	0.01667
ν_{23}	0.34

was determined by Gerbaud et al. (2019) by fitting the numerical results of 45° off-axis compression to the corresponding experimental curves at both quasi-static and dynamic rates, with axial strain rates of 0.0004 s⁻¹ and 280 s⁻¹, respectively. Gerbaud et al. (2019) have identified the visco-elastic parameters τ_1 and γ_1 based on 90° compression tests. Both visco-elastic and visco-plastic parameters are assumed to be independent of the hydrostatic pressure, being similar in tension and compression (Koerber et al., 2018; Gerbaud et al., 2019). The determination of the hardening curves needed to define the evolution of the yielding parameters expressed in Eqs. (46) to (51), along with the definition of the plastic potential parameters β_i , is detailed by Vogler et al. (2013) for the present material. The identification process of the hardening parameters α_i consists of relating the plastic strain in each loading state – transverse uniaxial loading, transverse biaxial loading and in-plane and transverse shear loading – to the equivalent plastic strain, here Eq. (53), using correction factors. These correction factors are directly dependent on the choice of the plastic potential parameters β_i , which are determined with recourse to a simplified optimisation procedure that ensures the desired plastic Poisson's ratio and plastic contractility. For more details about this identification process, the reader is referred to Vogler et al. (2013). The hardening curves describing the plasticity behaviour of IM7-8552 under uniaxial compression and in-plane shear are presented in Fig. 3. The elastic properties of this composite are summarised in Table 2.

Finite element explicit simulations are performed in Abaqus/Explicit (Abaqus, 2017). The specimens are modelled with eight-noded hexahedral elements with reduced integration (C3D8R), where the boundary conditions illustrated in Fig. 4 are prescribed. The dimensions of the finite element models are consistent with the dimensions of the specimens employed in the experimental tests performed by Koerber et al. (2010, 2018). As represented in Fig. 5, fine meshes are employed in the dynamic simulations to adequately capture different local strain rate values in distinct specimen regions. In contrast, coarser meshes are employed for quasi-static simulations (Koerber et al., 2018; Gerbaud et al., 2019). Additionally, an appropriate mass scaling is employed to alleviate the computational effort of quasi-static simulations by increasing the stable time increment without affecting the results (Gerbaud et al., 2019).

4.1.1. Results

The true stress–true strain curves of the off-axis compression simulation are presented in Figs. 6 to 11. The results of the off-axis tension simulation are presented in Figs. 12 to 15. The experimental curves reported by Koerber et al. (Koerber et al., 2010, 2018) have also been included in these figures.

The influence of the fibre orientation in the mechanical response is captured by the present model, revealing that the definition of free-energy function in terms of invariants deals appropriately with the transversely isotropic behaviour of this kind of material. More

4. Numerical results

4.1. Comparison and validation

The numerical results obtained with the current invariant-based constitutive model at finite strains are compared against experimental data and results obtained with the model of Gerbaud et al. (2019). The material HexPly IM7-8552 (carbon fibre with an epoxy matrix) has been experimentally characterised through longitudinal and off-axis tests, both in tension and compression loadings at different strain rates (Koerber et al., 2018, 2010). Strain rates above 100 s⁻¹ are achieved in dynamic tests, performed in Split-Hopkinson bar setups, while in quasi-static tests the strain rate values are of the order 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹. Therefore, this set of experimental results is adequate to assess the ability of the present model to capture the material behaviour for arbitrary stress states and at very different strain rates.

With regard to the material properties employed in the present simulations, the viscous parameters calibrated by Gerbaud et al. (2019) are employed here for a direct comparison with their numerical results (see Table 1). As reported by Koerber et al. (2018), the visco-plastic parameter m must be set to 1 since only two different load speeds are considered. Even though it represents a fair approximation for carbon–epoxy systems, the value of m should be calibrated by analysing at least three different strain rates for situations where thermoplastic matrices are used. The viscosity parameter $\eta = 3.5 \times 10^{-4}$ Ns/mm²

(a) Uniaxial compression

(b) In-plane shear

Fig. 3. Hardening curves employed to describe the plasticity behaviour of IM7-8552 (Vogler et al., 2013).

Fig. 4. Illustration of boundary conditions enforced to the finite element models.

(a) Quasi-static

(b) Dynamic

Fig. 5. Representation of meshes used in the simulations of 30° off-axis compression.

compliant responses are obtained with increasing off-axis angle and the non-linear behaviour is well captured, independently of the orientation of the fibres.

In the off-axis compression simulations, where visco-plasticity effects become more evident in the curves non-linearity, the yielding behaviour and pre-peak plastic response are well described, when comparing with the experimental results. This fact suggests that the yield criteria and plastic potential based on invariants are adequate. For the particular case of 30° and 45° off-axis compression and dynamic loading, the numerical model does not capture the stress peak and overestimates the stress when higher values of deformation are reached. In these cases, the experimental results show a loss of load-carrying capacity expressed by a stress plateau and beginning of strain-softening, which is related to damage mechanisms that are not accounted for in the present constitutive model. Damage onset and propagation can be included using, for instance, a strategy similar to Camanho et al. (2013), but considering the appropriate kinematics in finite strains.

The clear distinction between the curves obtained at different loading speeds demonstrates that this model captures strain-rate effects. Visco-elastic effects become evident when comparing the initial slope of the stress-strain curves, which is higher for the dynamic loadings. The influence of visco-plasticity is observed when comparing the values

Fig. 6. Axial true stress-true strain evolution for compression of specimens with 15°.

Fig. 7. Axial true stress-true strain evolution for compression of specimens with 30°.

Fig. 10. Axial true stress-true strain evolution for compression of specimens with 75°.

Fig. 8. Axial true stress-true strain evolution for compression of specimens with 45°.

Fig. 11. Axial true stress-true strain evolution for compression of specimens with 90°.

Fig. 9. Axial true stress-true strain evolution for compression of specimens with 60°.

Fig. 12. Axial true stress-true strain evolution for tension of specimens with 15°.

of stress at the yielding onset, which are also greater for the dynamic simulations.

In general, a good agreement between the experimental and numerical results is obtained with the current finite strain model. The results

obtained with this model are very close to the results obtained with the model proposed by Gerbaud et al. (2019), even though the kinematic description differs. The curves coincide for true strain values lower than 0.5%. This demonstrates that the current formulation recovers the

Fig. 13. Axial true stress–true strain evolution for tension of specimens with 30°.

Fig. 14. Axial true stress–true strain evolution for tension of specimens with 45°.

Fig. 15. Axial true stress–true strain evolution for tension of specimens with 90°.

formulation of Gerbaud et al. (2019) under small strain hypotheses. The differences between the numerical results in the large strain regime, up to 10%, are visible but relatively small. They may become more significant for larger values of strain. Nevertheless, these observations

suggest that the procedures employed by Vogler et al. (2013), Koerber et al. (2018) and Gerbaud et al. (2019) to calibrate the plasticity and viscosity-related parameters remain valid in the current finite strain approach.

4.2. Analysis of fibres re-orientation

Aiming to illustrate the importance of the finite strain-based kinematic description included in this model, local changes in the orientation of the fibres are analysed here. The current director vector at a generic time step $n + 1$ is computed in the VUMAT through:

$$\mathbf{a}_{n+1} = \mathbf{F}_{n+1} \mathbf{a}_0, \quad (83)$$

and it is stored in the model state variables. A comparison between the initial and final fibre orientations is depicted in Figs. 16 and 17, for the quasi-static off-axis 45° compression/tension. The final distribution of the orientation of the fibres in the deformed meshes is also represented in these figures. In order to obtain these representations, the Python script odb2vtk (Liu et al., 2017; Liu, 2016) has been modified to retrieve the state variables from Abaqus ODB files and convert the outputs for Paraview visualisation (ParaView, 2020).

A change in the orientation of the fibres is clearly observed in the compressive case, where the final orientation reaches 57.8° in some regions. The simulation has been repeated with a refined mesh to assess the influence of discretisation in such significant fibre re-orientation. The resulting distribution of the fibre angle is shown in Fig. 16(c), where it can be observed that similar values are obtained when comparing with Fig. 16(b). It has also been verified that the stress–strain curve remains similar. Therefore, the coarser mesh seems appropriate to describe this phenomenon in this case. In the tensile load, a minor re-orientation of the fibres in the loading direction is captured. The angle change is between -0.7° and -0.6° . This difference is mainly related to the strain undergone by the corresponding specimens. The compression specimens reach a true strain of more than 10%, whereas only 1.2% is observed in the case of tension (see Figs. 8 and 14). It is worth mentioning that experimental evidence has also showed higher magnitude of the fibre rotation for compression (1.3°) than for tension (0.35°) at ultimate strength (Koerber et al., 2010, 2018). Even though the current model overestimates these values, it does not include any damage or fracture mechanism, which are fundamental to accurately describe the material behaviour in the post-peak regime.

4.3. Local convergence rate

In this section, the impact of the stress update algorithm chosen within the local Newton–Raphson scheme is analysed by looking at the resulting convergence and computing time. Since the off-axis 45° compression example is the one that undergoes the most considerable deformations in both quasi-static and dynamic regimes, it is the focus of this analysis. Simulations with a single element model have been performed. Convergence of the Newton–Raphson iterative scheme is analysed in the last increment of the simulations for both the semi-implicit and fixed-point iterative algorithms, presented in Section 3.1. The relative difference measured between the guess and computed values of the isoclinic Mandel stress tensor, $\epsilon_{\bar{\Sigma}}$, is also reported. The convergence tolerance for both iterative schemes is $\epsilon_{tol} = \epsilon_{\bar{\Sigma},tol} = 10^{-6}$. The results are presented in Tables 3 and 4, for the semi-implicit and fixed-point approaches, respectively.

It is observed that relatively small elastic trial residuals are obtained in quasi-static simulations, regardless of the stress update approach. The local Newton–Raphson converges after the first iteration in this situation. The relative error associated with the isoclinic Mandel stress guess, $\epsilon_{\bar{\Sigma}}$, is negligible when the semi-implicit algorithm is employed (1.78×10^{-5}).

Fig. 16. Illustration of the final fibre orientation in the 45° off-axis quasi-static compression. (a) Comparison of initial (black arrow) and final (red arrow) fibres direction. (b) Final distribution of fibre angle values. (c) Final distribution of fibre angle values in a refined mesh. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 17. Illustration of the final fibre orientation in the 45° off-axis quasi-static tension. (a) Comparison of initial (black arrow) and final (red arrow) fibres direction. (b) Final distribution of fibre angle values. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

In contrast, the local Newton–Raphson requires more iterations to converge for dynamic simulations since the elastic trial residual is significant. With the semi-implicit approach, the relative error associated with the stress guess is not negligible in the initial iterations (1.13×10^{-2}). However, when convergence is achieved in the fifth iteration, the guess error becomes negligible (3.94×10^{-9}). Still, the error observed in the initial iterations impacts the Newton–Raphson convergence rate, which loses its quadratic convergence (c.f. second column of [Table 3](#)).

This issue is overcome by the fixed-point iterative method for fully implicit stress update. As observed in [Table 4](#), the quadratic convergence rate is kept for dynamic simulations. Nevertheless, this is obtained at the expense of additional iterations for the stress update: four in the second local iteration and 2 in the third.

In order to assess the impact of these observations on the actual computational cost, the computing time associated with the off-axis 45° compression simulations is presented in [Table 5](#). A fine mesh has been employed in the dynamic simulations, whereas a coarser has been used for the quasi-static simulations.

The resulting computing time is clearly reduced when the semi-implicit approach is employed, in spite of leading to a larger number of Newton–Raphson iterations, especially for dynamic simulations. For quasi-static simulations, where the simulation time is more significant, the semi-implicit approach should be employed to alleviate the computational cost. In the case of dynamic simulations, the fixed-point iterative approach is recommended to achieve a quadratic convergence rate and avoid premature simulation failure due to unsuccessful return

Table 3

Analysis of local convergence obtained with the semi-implicit stress update algorithm in off-axis 45° compression.

Quasi-static		
iteration (k)	residual ($r^{(k)}$)	stress relative difference ($\epsilon_{\bar{\epsilon}}$)
0 (elastic trial)	5.53×10^{-5}	
1	5.40×10^{-9}	1.78×10^{-5}
Dynamic		
iteration (k)	residual ($r^{(k)}$)	stress relative difference ($\epsilon_{\bar{\epsilon}}$)
0 (elastic trial)	1.88×10^0	
1	6.14×10^{-4}	1.13×10^{-2}
2	2.09×10^{-3}	1.64×10^{-4}
3	7.34×10^{-5}	1.43×10^{-5}
4	1.21×10^{-6}	2.41×10^{-7}
5	2.53×10^{-8}	3.94×10^{-9}

Table 4

Analysis of local convergence obtained with the fixed-point iterative algorithm for fully-implicit stress update in off-axis 45° compression.

Quasi-static			
local Newton–Raphson		Fixed-point iterations	
iteration (k)	residual ($r^{(k)}$)	iteration (l)	relative difference ($\epsilon_{\bar{\epsilon}}$)
0 (elastic trial)	6.10×10^{-5}		
1	1.91×10^{-9}	1	1.98×10^{-5}
		2	4.99×10^{-10}
Dynamic			
local Newton–Raphson		Fixed-point iterations	
iteration (k)	residual ($r^{(k)}$)	iteration (l)	relative difference ($\epsilon_{\bar{\epsilon}}$)
0 (elastic trial)	1.90×10^0		
1	2.69×10^{-3}	1	1.37×10^{-2}
		2	2.38×10^{-4}
		3	4.20×10^{-6}
		4	7.49×10^{-8}
2	7.15×10^{-8}	1	1.93×10^{-5}
		2	3.32×10^{-7}

Table 5

Computing time associated with off-axis 45° compression simulations, for each stress update approach.

	Semi-implicit	Fixed-point iterative
Quasi-static	6 min 39 s (399 s)	8 min 14 s (494 s)
Dynamic	21 s	24 s

mapping. Despite leading to higher computational cost, the computing times in this kind of simulation are relatively small and the additional cost is almost negligible in practice.

5. Conclusions

An invariant-based constitutive model for unidirectional fibre-reinforced composites subjected to finite strains, considering visco-elastic and visco-plastic effects, has been proposed and implemented. The constitutive equations are expressed in terms of quantities defined in the isoclinic configuration. Therefore, changes in fibres orientation are implicitly accounted for in the model. A backward-Euler implicit scheme is employed to integrate the evolution laws. A semi-implicit and a fixed-point iterative fully implicit approach are proposed to perform the stress update within the implicit scheme. Analysis of the performance of these algorithms reveals that the semi-implicit approach results in faster simulations. Nevertheless, the fixed-point iterative fully implicit stress update is recommended for simulations involving high strain rate loadings since it guarantees the quadratic convergence of the local Newton–Raphson scheme. The numerical results of simulations involving off-axis tension and compression at different strain rates are in close agreement with experimental data.

The present model can predict visco-elastic and visco-plastic effects in arbitrary loading directions. A comparison reveals that the current model recovers the model of Gerbaud et al. (2019) for true strain values up to 0.5%. Relative minor deviations are observed for more significant deformations. The suitability of this model to capture changes in fibres orientations has been illustrated. The results suggest that the enhanced kinematical description may play a more decisive role in the prediction of the behaviour of polymer composites undergoing larger strains. When comparing with experimental data, the predicted fibre rotation is overestimated. However, the present model does not consider damage or fracture, which may explain these differences. This topic will be addressed in future work.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledge the funding received from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking (JU), through the project TREAL — Thermoplastic material allowable generation using a reliability-based virtual modeling platform (Grant agreement No. 864723). The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Clean Sky 2 JU members other than the Union. The present contribution reflects only the authors' view. The JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Pedro P. Camanho acknowledges the support of FCT — Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P., in the scope of the project UIDB/50022/2020.

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